
Plato's *Republic*: The Limits of Politics

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Abstract: Plato's *Republic*, as the dialogue is known in English, is a classic, perhaps *the* classic investigation of the reasons why human beings form political communities—or “cities” in his terms. In the *Republic* Socrates inquires into the origins of the city in order to discover what justice “writ big” is. But in the process of constructing his “city”—or, actually, “cities”—“in speech,” Socrates does not offer us a definition of justice so much as he shows us the reasons why no actual city is ever apt to be perfectly just. From Plato's *Republic* we thus understand why justice is difficult, if not impossible to achieve for communities, but may be a virtue of private individuals.

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Plato's *Republic*, as the dialogue is known in English, is a classic, perhaps *the* classic investigation of the reasons why human beings form political communities—or “cities” in his terms. In the *Republic* (368c-369a) Socrates inquires into the origins of the city in order to discover what justice “writ big” is. However, in the process of constructing his “city in speech,” Socrates does not offer us a definition of justice so much as he shows us the reasons why no actual city is ever apt to be perfectly just. In other words, from Plato's *Republic* we learn something about the limits of politics that make justice difficult, if not impossible to achieve for communities, if not for private individuals.

What we first learn from Socrates' attempt to discover what justice is by looking for it “writ big” in a city is that, like the city itself, justice arises out of a certain kind of necessity. The unstated implication is that justice is not desirable in itself.

Cities arise, Socrates points out (369b), because individual human beings are not self-sufficient. Because everyone has more needs than he or she can easily supply for him or herself, people gather together. Instead of everyone trying to fulfill his or her basic needs for food, clothing, and housing, people quickly learn that it works better for each to do what he or she does best and to trade their surplus with others. What Socrates calls the “true” and “healthy” city is thus characterized by a division of labor and specialization. And that division extends beyond the provision of what might be considered to be the most basic needs—food, clothing, and shelter—to the manufacture of tools, for example, plows for farming, as well to trade. It thus includes merchants, sailors, and money as well as wage-labor. (369c-371e)

The way in which this first “true” city embodies the principle of justice does not become clear until later, because when Socrates asks Adeimantus whether this first city is complete, and where justice and injustice are to be found in it, Adeimantus is not sure. But the simple life Socrates goes on to describe—of people making the food, clothing, and shelter they need, naked and shoeless in the summer, but clothed and housed in the winter, and with enough to relax, feast, and drink to the gods in the evening, as well as to have sweet intercourse with one another—sounds almost idyllic (372a-c). It is a vision to which many subsequent thinkers have returned. It is, therefore, worth our while to look more carefully at what Socrates calls the true city. *The* principle of justice Socrates and his interlocutors later find “rolling around at their feet” (432d-433a) turns out to be *the* organizing principle of the first, true city. It is the principle of the division of labor and specialization—namely, that each should do what he or she does best by nature and share or exchange the benefits.

Why is this the first and perhaps most fundamental rule of justice? There are two reasons, I would suggest. First, when each does what he or she does best by nature, and they share or exchange the fruits of their labor, everyone benefits. In other words, under this arrangement the good of the individual and the good of the community are the same. There is no question of someone taking advantage of someone else by force or by fraud. However, the harmony of individual and social good in this simple city is not solely or automatically a product of the division of labor and specialization per se. In most actual divisions, the tasks and the rewards are not equal. Some people, usually poor and uneducated, are forced by economic necessity if not outright coercion to perform tasks that maim rather than fulfill them. Other people reap more of the benefits. For the division of labor to be just, Socrates thus insists that it be based upon differences in natural inclinations or talents. Because each does what he or she is naturally inclined to do, each presumably contributes his or her part spontaneously and voluntarily. No one forces someone else to work; no one decides what other members of the community must do. Everyone contributes his or her bit to the good of the community as a whole, *and* everyone enjoys the same benefits or rewards. That is possible, we soon learn, only when all members of the community restrict their desires and consumption to what they need. No luxury or surplus can be allowed.

Reflecting on the embodiment of what Socrates later identifies as the principle of justice in this first “true” city, we can already see three important elements, if not prob-

lems. First, justice arises not as a matter of choice or something desirable so much as a necessity imposed by the limitations or weaknesses of individual human beings. Second, insofar as the justice of the division of labor rests on differences of natural talents, it rests on an abstract generalization. As Socrates says, we observe that different individuals perform various tasks more or less easily. It is not the case, however, that any individual human being is as uni-dimensional or single-talented as Socrates suggests. Some people can do many things well; others can perform few, if any tasks well. It is not possible, moreover, to see or know what any individual can do easily or well until he or she does it. Some tasks require great physical strength; others presuppose good memories or facility with words. The relevant differences in natural aptitude may be more visible in the simple city than they are in more complex economies and civilization. (No one can know until a person has been highly educated and trained whether she will become a great mathematician or pianist, for example.) But even in the simple city, aptitude per se is not visible; and individuals will, in fact, be able to do more than one thing. Nature does not provide as much direction as Socrates suggests. But where the allocation of tasks is not based on natural differences, it is not clearly or unambiguously just.

Glaucon famously raises a third fundamental problem by declaring that the first “true” city is a “city of pigs” (372d). Put simply, Glaucon’s point is that human beings are not satisfied merely with what they need to survive comfortably. We want more. We do not simply desire more basic goods to secure us against future wants; we desire services and goods that are not necessary for our self-preservation. We want luxuries like servants, artists, various kinds of adornment, entertainment, honors, and learning. (372e-373c) Arising more from our imagination and intellect than from simple need, these “luxuries” include activities like poetry that we often define as distinctively human.

Socrates does not say whether he thinks such ever-expanding human desire is natural. But, by characterizing a city animated by desire for non-necessary goods as “feverish” in contrast to the “healthy” city he first described, Socrates suggests that such a city is “sick” and thus in danger of disintegrating. He does not deny, however, that some, if not all human beings are moved by a desire to have more than they need merely to survive. Indeed, he points out that in this desire they have found the origin of both war and injustice. (373e)

Because human desires are not limited to the requirements of self-preservation, whether of the individual or of the species, as one might argue animals are instinctively regulated, more complex civic institutions become necessary. So, Socrates observes, even if the citizens of a “healthy” city are satisfied with what they need, they will find themselves destroyed by others if they do not provide for the common defense. And, fighting wars successfully requires knowledge, skill, or art. Following the principle that each person should perform the task or art for which he or she is best suited by nature, Socrates and his interlocutors are thus led to ask, what sort of person is best able by nature to defend or guard the city? Just as we have seen that human desires in general are directed not merely to what is necessary for survival and so to a just

division of labor, but also to what is not necessary and thus to the unjust seizure of the goods of others, so we now see that the defenders of cities need to have a double nature, characterized by what appear to be opposed inclinations.¹ Simply stated, the guardians need to be gentle to their fellow citizens, but harsh toward enemies. Socrates thus admits, in effect, that human nature is not as uni-dimensional or uni-directed, as his first true city presupposed.

Socrates also admits, in effect, that justice or order may spontaneously arise as a matter of necessity, but it cannot and will not be spontaneously or automatically maintained after the requirements of mere preservation are met. Human beings do not naturally live at peace with one another, because we are naturally drawn—both as individuals and in communities—in opposite directions.

The practical problem that arises as soon as we recognize the need for some members of a community to be armed to defend the whole remains all-too-familiar. The arms that enable some members of the citizen body to defend the rest can be used just as well—indeed, even more easily—to oppress the other members of their own community without arms. Military dictatorships and corrupt policemen are still all-too-common. (E.g., Syria or, perhaps closer to home, the Mafia.) Like Socrates we thus have an immediate interest in asking how we can prevent the armed from oppressing their unarmed fellows. Like Socrates and his interlocutors, we also need to persuade both our military forces and the police not only to risk their lives in order to protect the lives of others but also to believe that it would be wrong for them to seize power as the reward they are due for protecting the rest of us.

To prevent those with arms from using them to oppress the unarmed, Socrates suggests, it is necessary to regulate their education from birth. Because guardians will have to risk their lives in order to defend the city, they should also not be allowed to hear stories about the terrors of the afterlife that might make them afraid to die. Nor should they be presented with images of gods or heroes engaging in immoderate behavior—whether that be lamentations for the loss of a beloved son or friend, excessive eating and drinking, or even laughter. (386a-391e)

By forbidding the expression of a desire for anything more than people need in order to survive comfortably, Socrates’ second, defensive city might seem to have returned, at least domestically, to his first “true” city, characterized by free and equal economic exchange. There is, however, a crucial difference between the first “true” and “healthy” city, in which people voluntarily supply and exchange the goods and services they need on the basis of their own various natural inclinations, and the second “purged” city (399e), in which the natural desire people have to do and possess more than what is necessary to preserve themselves has to be intentionally and repeatedly repressed.

The tension or gap between the good of the individual and the good of the community becomes evident—especially when Socrates turns from the guardians’ education in music to “gymnastics.” Although every citizen is supposed to do what he or she does best by nature, Socrates points out, they will not be training and conditioning guardians to fight in defense of the city the way athletes are trained and conditioned for gymnastic contests, even

though such athletes would appear to be those best suited by nature to bodily exercises. In order to perform well in specific contests, Socrates reminds his interlocutors, athletes have to follow a strict regimen of eating and sleeping. But, in order to fight defensively, soldiers have to be conditioned to go without food or sleep. (404a-b) In Socrates' second, "purged city" it is no longer simply the citizens' natural inclinations or talents that determine what they do and learn, but their specific function in and for the city. Turning from the guardians' formative gymnastic training to remedial care of their bodies or medicine, Socrates thus enunciates a very harsh doctrine. In the purged city doctors will not be allowed to acquire as much knowledge as possible about ways of preserving life. The goal of the purged city is no longer the preservation of individuals, as it was initially in the "true" city. The goal has become instead the preservation of the community. Individual human beings who are not able to perform their functions are to be left to die. (404e-408b) If justice is to be found in this second, "purged" city, it appears to consist in putting the interest of the community or the "common good" above that of the individual. Such a stance would seem to be characteristic of a soldier who risks his life in defending his city and family. But, we should ask, is this justice? And if it is, is justice a virtue that is choiceworthy in and of itself?

Liberals are apt to object to the obvious deprivation of freedom of thought and expression Socrates has mandated to "purge" his city.² But, even if one takes the education Socrates proposes in its own terms, one can ask whether it is apt to produce the desired results. Will soldiers be truly courageous—or even disciplined, for that matter—if they do not fear death? Will people who have never been exposed to excess or luxury be able to restrain their desires, if and when they have an opportunity to indulge them? Would human beings really want to live in a society where laughter is forbidden?

As Socrates makes clear in his description of the rude medicine they will allow in the city, the point of the education of the guardians is not to make them knowledgeable. It is rather to develop and harmonize both their harsh and gentle sides so that they can serve as guardians. And that means, primarily, that they must be inculcated with right opinions. Above all, Socrates emphasizes, guardians must be taught to love the city, because a person will "surely love something most when he believes that the same things are advantageous to it and to himself" (412d). The second, "purged" city Socrates has sketched is not characterized by freedom of thought. Nor is it simply based on the truth. On the contrary, Socrates informs his interlocutors, instituting such a "just" city will require them to tell a "well-born lie" that has two parts: the citizens must all be persuaded, first, that they are all brothers and sisters, children of the land they occupy; and, second, that they are all born with different metallic bloods—gold, silver, iron, and bronze—that determine the specific functions they will perform in the city as rulers, soldiers, farmers or mechanics.³ The need for such a lie points to the two ways in which no particular "city" or political community will ever be perfectly just: 1) no people has an unambiguous right to occupy any particular part of the earth to the exclusion of all others; and 2) allocations of necessary tasks in any community will never

simply or completely correspond to the desires and inclinations of individuals.

The "justice" of Socrates' second, "purged" city consists in the complete subordination of the desires of the individual citizens to the needs of the community as a whole. In order to achieve the common good, Socrates suggests, the community should be as unified as it can be. If it were possible, all citizens should feel the pain, if any one pricks her finger. (462b-d) No one should be aware of any difference that divides him or her from others. To achieve maximal unity, Socrates explains, it will not suffice to persuade citizens that they are all members of the same family and born to perform a certain function. The guardians—that is to say, those with the arms that would enable them to oppress their fellow citizens—must be deprived not merely of all private property, but of all privacy. They and their domiciles must always be open to public inspection. (416d) They must not be allowed to develop any private interests or affections that might qualify their complete dedication to the common good.

To make sure that all members of the community serve in the capacity for which they are best suited by nature, Socrates adds, males and females must be given the same education—and subjected to the same tests to determine who should learn and perform which of the necessary tasks. (451d-452a) To free females from the burdens of child-rearing as well as to prevent the development of particular attachments that would compromise citizens' whole-hearted dedication to the community, children must also be reared in common, without knowledge of their parents or their parents knowing which children are theirs. (457d-460d)

Socrates expects that there will be resistance to his proposals to abolish private property and households or families, as we know them. His suggestion that they destroy what we now call the nuclear family has been decried as "unnatural," but Socrates suggests that common notions about gender roles or the division of labor between the sexes are highly conventional. (The *Republic* is a very radical book; there was nothing really like it again until the 19th century when some of the proposals Socrates makes for the sake of argument, were seriously proposed as actual reforms.)

Because the proposition that friends hold all things in common was an old adage (even in ancient Greece), Socrates thinks that his third, most novel proposal will provoke the most outrage and opposition. And, surely, his advocacy of "philosopher-kings" (or queens, according to the argument) has proved to be the single most distinctive and famous feature of the *Republic*.⁴ But, why, we should ask does Socrates insist that the rule of philosophers will be necessary to bring a truly just society into existence? Strictly speaking, he observes that the least change in any existing city that would be required to make it truly just would be for a ruler to become a philosopher, or a philosopher to become a ruler. (473c-d) However, we still confront the question, why? At first it looks as if the philosophers possess the knowledge required to found and maintain such a city. Specifically, they are said to know the forms of the virtues, i.e., what human excellence is, and how to foster it. (500c-501b) What that means, in effect, is that they know what human potential is—both in general and in the case of specific individuals. Such phi-

losophers would presumably be able to assign individual citizens the tasks for which they are best suited by nature, because these philosophers would know the nature of each as well as of the species as a whole. *If* human beings were programmed by nature to perform a specific task, as Socrates suggested in his initial description of the “true” city, it would be possible for a ruler to allocate tasks on the basis of his or her knowledge of nature. But, in fact, we know that human beings are not so clearly directed by nature or to a single task.

Not surprisingly, therefore, Socrates introduces another reason why philosophers would make the only just rulers: philosophers are the only human beings who cannot use rule to obtain what they most desire. (520d-521a) As lovers of wisdom, philosophers do not possess knowledge so much as seek it. And, Socrates argues, their overwhelming love of truth makes philosophers relatively immune to the fear of death and desires for wealth and reputation that lead other human beings to be unjust. (484d-486c) However, Socrates acknowledges, that very love of truth also makes philosophers not merely uninterested, but positively unwilling to rule, because ruling would constitute an unwelcome distraction from their search for knowledge. Only if they feel compelled to rule by their own sense of justice, which tells them that they owe the city service in return for the education the city provided them that enabled them to become philosophers. But here’s the catch—or vicious circle. Philosophers won’t incur such an obligation for serving the city in return for the education they have received from it—unless their city is already ruled by philosophers. But philosophers who were not themselves educated by the city would not want to rule—and non-philosophers wouldn’t understand the reasons why they should force the philosophers to rule. Nor, in fact, could they. No one can force someone else to pay attention to a particular set of concerns.

So, where does Socrates—or Plato—leave us? By spelling out the requirements of establishing a just political community, Socrates has both indicated what justice *per se* would require and why human beings are never apt to achieve it. 1) Socrates announced the first and most fundamental requirement of justice in his initial description of the “true” city: there must not be a conflict between the natural inclinations and good of the individuals who compose the city and the good of the community. 2) Unfortunately, as Glaucon’s protest against the “city of pigs” indicates, the natural inclinations, talents, and good of individual human beings are not as easily known, as Socrates seems to suggest. Once their basic needs are satisfied, human beings are easily led to imagine and wish for unnecessary luxuries, and to try to seize the goods of others unjustly in order to satisfy their new desires. 3) The unarmed, innocent inhabitants of cities thus require the protection of armed soldiers or policemen against unjust foreign aggressors and domestic criminals; and to prevent these armed guards from misusing their power, they must be persuaded not to fear death or to desire pleasure to excess. But, Socrates also admits, attempts to convince human beings not to fear death or desire pleasure won’t work. People will seek their own good at the expense of others unless they are subject to constant supervision. And who is to supervise the supervisors? Won’t the su-

pervisors or rulers use their power to seek their own good? Unless they are philosophers, who don’t seek to rule, because of their own peculiar nature and understanding of the good, they will.

As Socrates indicates when he describes the degeneration of the just city, the “aristocrats” who believe that they are better born or have “better blood,” than their fellow citizens are apt to use their arms to force the “lower born” to work for them. These “timocrats” thus accumulate private property, even slaves, and try to perpetuate their bloodline by means of their own offspring. (545c-547c) Children will not be reared, nurtured and educated in common; and, as a result, women will not be educated the same way as men. In other words, absent the rule of philosophers, human beings develop the kinds of unjust regimes we have seen in history. Because they are not philosophers, the so-called “aristocrats” do not understand what true human excellence is. Mistaking it for the honor granted by others or, more frequently, for wealth, “aristocracies” degenerate into “oligarchies”; and the worship of wealth characteristic of oligarchies gradually produces a lack of restraint. People seek wealth in order to live as they please, and when they exhaust their own or their families’ resources, they seek control of the government to seize the resources of others.

What is at the bottom or the cause of this tendency for political communities to spiral downward into injustice, especially as they become wealthier and more powerful? The reason we see in reviewing Socrates’ account of the origin of both justice and injustice in the first “healthy” and then “feverish” cities-in-speech he describes is that in his first sketch of the “true” city he recognizes only the natural forces that work to bring human beings together for their mutual benefit—our lack of self-sufficiency as individuals and the advantages of an exchange of goods produced by a division of labor based on differences in natural talents and inclinations. What Socrates is only grudgingly and half-heartedly forced to admit in responding to the questions of his interlocutors is that this simple economic community constituted on the basis of wholly voluntary exchanges—the model still at the root of modern “market” economics—can be maintained only if people limit their desires to what is necessary to live comfortably and at peace. But, as we have also been reminded, people are easily led to desire more than they need—and consequently to become unjust.

Socrates admits that his attempt to purge the citizens of his city-in-speech of all such desires won’t work, but he does not specify the reasons why. He points—but only points—to the first reason when he asserts that it would be desirable for the city to become so unified that if any citizen feels pain, all do. Socrates says that creating such a literally common feeling would be desirable, but he doesn’t claim that it is possible. He knows that, in fact, no human being can feel the pain of another; at most we can imagine and empathize with it. And because we literally do not feel the pain of another, we do not care as much about that imagined pain as we would if we ourselves were suffering. In sum, as embodied beings, human beings all exist separately from others. The goods of the body can be distributed, but they can’t literally be shared. Only intellectual or purely intelligible goods can be shared with others without any loss. There are, therefore,

fundamental natural limits to the extent to which human beings, even “friends” can hold all things in common.

Moreover, when the good in question is life or the preservation thereof, not merely of the individual, but of the community, Socrates' attempt to unify the city by forcing its inhabitants to share everything comes into conflict with another very natural human characteristic. Young male human beings may become sexually aroused relatively easily, but they do not perform on command. Nor, because sexual desire in human beings is so closely tied to the imagination, are human beings indifferent to their partners. It would be difficult to breed and raise human beings, as if we were dogs. Socrates makes the radical proposals he does about the breeding and nurturing of citizens in common in order to provide females with the education they need in order to develop their individual natural talents. His proposals thus recognize and privilege one sort of natural difference—particularly in the intellectual abilities necessary to learn different skills or “arts”—at the expense of another, the obvious natural difference between members of the two sexes with regard to procreative functions.

Even if it were possible, as it may now seem to be, to overcome this natural difference by means of technology, Aristotle's criticism of the communal institutions proposed in Plato's *Republic* would still hold. (*Pol.* 2.1261a10-1264b15) When property or other things are held in common, Aristotle observes, no one in particular feels responsible for caring for them. So, rather than everyone caring equally for everyone in the community—or feeling together—no one cares or feels anything much for anything or anybody else. This phenomenon is now known as the “tragedy of the commons” in rational choice theory. And it has much more devastating effects with regard to the care for people than for public resources or parks. Public, government sponsored or required “care” for the elderly or young is notoriously cold, officious, bureaucratic and unfeeling. The fact is that human beings care first and most about themselves, and, second, about those they hold particularly close to them, friends and family. As Aristotle sees it, this care about oneself and one's family is the source and foundation of politics—rather than the division of labor based on natural differences to which Socrates points. (*Pol.* 1.1252a24-1253a29) But whether it is the source or merely a serious complication, the attachment human beings feel to themselves and “their own” is the chief and enduring obstacle not only to the establishment of a completely just community but also to the establishment of a world community encompassing all members of the human species or family. This observation does not mean that there is nothing human beings can do to make their political communities more just or caring. Philosophers like Plato, Aristotle, and their many successors would not have asked what is just, if people did not want to know and to use their knowledge to improve their own lives and communities. Recognizing both the power and the importance of self-love and particularistic affection should, however, make us conscious of the limits of our power and hesitate to impose the same rules on everyone, everywhere for the sake of achieving a too abstract understanding of justice.

Notes

¹ See Hans Georg Gadamer, “Plato and the Poets,” *Dialogue and Dialectic*, trans. P. Christopher Smith (New Haven: Yale University Press, 1980), 54-55 (*Gesammelte Werke* V:198-99), who argues that Socrates thus shows that human existence is both political and historical.

² E.g., Karl R. Popper, *The Open Society and Its Enemies* (Princeton: Princeton University Press, 1950).

³ I translate γεννάσιον (414a) literally as “well-born,” because the *lie* concerns birth literally and is not described as καλόν.

⁴ C. D. C. Reeve, *Philosopher-kings* (Princeton: Princeton University Press, 1988); Leo Strauss, “On Plato's Republic,” *The City and Man* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1964), 50-138.